

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

Insights from the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue at the Second Annual HERCCULES Meeting

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2025 – Vernasca, Italy

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Insights from the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue at the Second Annual HERCCULES Meeting

Work Package Lead beneficiary Dissemination level Abstract	WP8 Fraunhofer ISI (FRAU) Public This report summarises key insights from the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue held during the Second Annual Meeting of the HERCCULES project in Vernasca, Italy on July 1 st and 2 nd , 2025.
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1 Introduction

This brief report synthesises key insights from the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue held during the Second Annual HERCCULES Meeting. The interactive session brought together participants from across the HERCCULES consortium, representing diverse backgrounds ranging from technical to socio-scientific disciplines. On-site participants were divided into four groups and invited to reflect on three guiding questions concerning their past experiences with community engagement around CCUS and beyond, their lessons learned, and their recommendations for community engagement activities in HERCCULES. Online participants were also encouraged to contribute their insights to the workshop organisers. Each guiding question was discussed for five minutes, after which the on-site participants documented the main points and presented a two-minute summary. These summaries, together with the documented group notes, form the primary input for this report.

The goal was to integrate diverse experiences and perspectives regarding ongoing CCUS community engagement activities within Work Package 8 (Social Perception and Community Engagement).

The following sections summarise the discussions, drawing on partners past experiences and lessons learned to derive recommendations for future community engagement activities in HERCCULES, followed by concluding remarks.

2 Past experiences with community engagement and lessons learned

HERCCULES consortium partners have already carried out a wide range of community engagement activities around CCUS and related energy or industrial projects. They organised site visits, plant tours, and open-door events to give local communities insight into their facilities. Their educational activities included interactive lectures in schools and universities, often combined with competitions or prizes to actively involve students.¹ Project updates and general information were further disseminated through social media, dedicated websites², TV interviews³, and media features⁴. Furthermore, their community engagement efforts also involved formal and informal stakeholder dialogues.⁵ Public consultations were conducted as part of environmental impact assessments, using both local conferences and online platforms to collect questions and concerns. Partners also collaborated with local companies, the press, and social media influencers to ensure clear communication and to counter misinformation.⁶ Finally, they also engaged with policymakers across spatial levels.

¹ See for example, activities by SHOGenenergy, such as different educational courses [\[1\]](#), [\[2\]](#), [\[3\]](#). Moreover, the University of Utrecht is engaging master students of [Energy Science](#) through both coursework and master theses processes. Similarly POLIMI's Department of Energy and School of Design organised and delivered a [workshop to provide knowledge on CCUS to students in 2024](#).

² See for example, [ENERGEAN website with references to the HERCCULES project](#) and specific information about the [Prinos Carbon Storage](#).

³ See for example, a SHOGenenergy [interview on the Estonian TV channel EVS+](#)

⁴ See for example, contribution to [media coverage in Greece by ENERGEAN](#),

⁵ See for example, participation of ENERGEAN in the [International Forum on Recent Cross-Cutting Developments in CCU/CCS](#) and the [HERCCULES Dissemination Event in Tallinn in 2024](#) involving stakeholders; and [SHOGenenergy's participation in the EU CCUS Forum 2023](#), [the BFC-2023 Baltic Carbon Forum](#), and the [BCF 2024 Baltic Carbon Forum](#). Moreover, HERCCULES is engaging with regional CCS stakeholders on a regular basis as part of the project's Regional Stakeholder Committees (an activity within WP8). See for example the [regional stakeholder committee meeting in Bologna](#).

⁶ See for example the [training on CCUS for Italian journalists in Milan in 2025](#)

When asked about the lessons learned from their previous community engagement activities, the participants of the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue emphasised that effective community engagement at a regional level requires the **strategic involvement of multiple stakeholder groups**. In their experience, relevant stakeholders that should be targeted in community engagement campaigns include:

- 1) The local general public, for example through neighbourhood or social committees, or through local conferences to gather and respond to concerns.
- 2) Municipal authorities, councils, and mayors, as local political leaders often reflect and amplify public concern.
- 3) The media, which might sometimes hold openly critical views and play a crucial role in shaping public perception. The same applies to social media influencers, who are particularly relevant for reaching younger audiences.
- 4) Industry associations, chambers of commerce, and permitting authorities, who can facilitate regulatory processes or act as intermediaries.

In terms of **strategies for the design of effective community engagement**, the following aspects were highlighted:

- 1) Getting stakeholders involved early on. This is expected to help prevent negative stories from spreading, especially among political leaders.
- 2) Community engagement should be led by independent actors (e.g. research organisations) to gain credibility and avoid accusations of manipulation or greenwashing. While companies have a supporting role, their engagement on the frontline of messaging, especially on sensitive issues, might sometimes be counterproductive.
- 3) Educational outreach on climate change, CCUS, and its role in hard-to-abate industries should be conducted. This could be done through lectures in schools and universities (potentially with the involvement of influencers), open door events and plant visits, as well as interactive websites and events (e.g. competitions between schools).

The community engagement strategies outlined above could be accompanied by further **measures to strengthen acceptance** and foster long-term trust such as offering local benefits and financial incentives, as seen in successful onshore wind projects. Furthermore, strategic partnerships with local organisations, including education, industry, and press, can be pursued to implement some of the strategies described above and to foster a shared understanding.

3 Recommendations for community engagement activities in HERCCULES

Drawing on their past experiences and lessons learned, participants in the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue shared several **recommendations to support the design and implementation of meaningful, effective, and relevant community engagement in the HERCCULES project**. These recommendations are intended to guide the work of partners involved in Work Package 8 (Social Perception and Community Engagement) as they continue to engage with communities in the HERCCULES regions on CCUS.

Key recommendations from the HERCCULES consortium partners involved in the dialogue include the following:

1) Ensure transparency and communicate credibly.

Community engagement in the HERCCULES project should prioritise transparency and the dissemination of up-to-date, high-quality technical and socio-scientific information. In line with the project consortium's summary of key learnings (see Section 2), involving independent

actors, such as researchers, NGOs, media outlets, and social media influencers, can enhance the trustworthiness and credibility of community engagement activities within the project. These actors can also communicate the benefits of CCUS technologies, including their contribution to economic opportunities, job creation, improved infrastructure, energy security, climate change mitigation, and sustainable development.

2) Use clear, simple language and visualisations.

Simplicity in language and effective visual communication were identified as essential. Public outreach and education efforts should explain how CCUS works in an accessible way, starting with the basics of climate change and energy before introducing the technology itself. This foundational understanding can help to counteract misinformation and resolve polarising narratives (e.g. the perception that the deployment of CCUS and renewables are opposing strategies, or that CCUS is a means of greenwashing or that CO₂ storage is waste disposal). Clear communication is also vital when discussing related technologies, such as clarifying the origin of hydrogen to avoid the assumption that it is automatically “green”.

3) Acknowledge and address perceived risks and concerns.

Concerns regarding storage (e.g. leakage or seismic activity) and transportation (e.g. accidents involving pipelines or trucks) should be taken seriously, even if they might seem uninformed or emotional to technical professionals. Open dialogue with local communities is therefore crucial. The HERCCULES project team should explain the monitoring systems in place, demonstrate how risks are managed, and convey their technical competence and responsibility. This approach fosters transparency and builds public trust.

4) Foster inclusive, interactive engagement.

Community engagement within the HERCCULES project should be open and inclusive, allowing space for questions, diverse perspectives and creative ideas. One suggested way to improve community connection is to use promotional materials to raise awareness.

Overall, the participants of the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue highlighted that it is relevant to get the conversation started. If one person knows about CCUS, they can raise awareness among others. It is important to communicate the benefits of the technology but also take concerns of the public and different stakeholders seriously and engage in an open and transparent exchange. According to the participants of the dialogue, potential **further outlets and arenas for community engagement activities** within the HERCCULES project could include training events, CCUS days, music events, sports events, distributing flyers, and displaying models of the plants and videos.

4 Concluding remarks

In summary, while the insights presented consolidate a range of perspectives and offer valuable direction for community engagement strategies, it should be noted that the **reflections are drawn exclusively from members of the HERCCULES project consortium** and might not represent broader or more diverse viewpoints. Therefore, caution should be exercised when generalising these findings to other projects or contexts.

That said, **several key themes emerged with broad agreement among participants of the trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue.** These themes include the fundamental role of trust, necessitating the use of credible and neutral messengers; the necessity of tailoring messages to specific audiences; the critical importance of acknowledging and responding to community concerns; and the importance of designing and implementing flexible, open-minded community engagement. These findings will inform ongoing community engagement efforts within the HERCCULES project and might also be useful for other projects seeking to foster meaningful community involvement.

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